

Hydrophobic Hydration of Synthetic Humic Acids

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An attempt has been made to understand the folding-unfolding behaviour of natural humic acid-like synthetic substances in terms of the solute-solvent interaction term, the B -coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation. The $B_{\text{expt}}/B_{\text{theo}}$ ratio is supposed to be in the range of the ratio of exposed surface area of the coiled system to that of linear chain which was computed earlier to be $1/\pi$. It is observed that there is deviation of this ratio from the ideal value of $1/\pi$, with the deviation depending not only on hydrophilic polar head groups of the synthetic substances but also on aliphatic and aromatic parts of humic substances due to 'hydrophobic hydration' phenomenon. It is also observed that the higher value of $(-\delta Y / \delta \ln C)$ in the surface property measurement contributes positively to hydrophobic hydration through its structure-making effect, resulting in a higher B -terms ratio and a greater degree of condensation, as indicated by lower (E_4/E_6) ratio.

The change in the viscosity due to the interaction between the solute and the solvent is taken into account in B -coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation¹ for dilute solution of electrolytes,

$$\eta_{\text{sp}} / \sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C}$$

This B -term can be approximated² to intrinsic viscosity obtained from Fuoss-Strauss equation³ for non-electrolytes,

$$\eta_{\text{sp}} / C = A' (1 + B\sqrt{C})$$

The B -term of Jones-Dole equation is correlated to different viscous phenomena⁴, namely,

$$\eta_E + \eta_{\text{or}} + \eta_{\text{str}} = \eta_0 BC$$

where, η_E is the Einstein effect due to shape and size of ions resulting in an increase in viscosity, η_{or} the orientation effect of polar molecules of the solvent by electric field leading to increase in viscosity, and η_{str} the structural decomposition of solvent in bulk phase due to field of ions on solvent molecules bound to ions in certain orientation causing decrease in viscosity. The B -term is positive when $\eta_E + \eta_{\text{or}} \gg \eta_{\text{str}}$.

The dissolution of non-polar molecules in water causes general strengthening of water structure arising from the loss in entropy of water and this phe-

nomenon is known as 'hydrophobic hydration'^{4,5}. The large hydrophobic peripheral surface of humic acid molecule may causes significant increase in local viscosity and B -term value through hydrophobic hydration^{5,6}, and the larger the hydrocarbon chain, the greater is this effect. But there is a partial loss of this structure-making effect in aromatic compounds in comparison with open-chain hydrocarbons having the same number of carbon atoms⁶. This is due to the inability of water molecules to accommodate themselves for spatial restrictions inside the aromatic ring⁶. Further, the presence of the π -electron cloud above and below the plane of the aromatic ring facilitates the breakdown of water-cluster adjacent to the rings by transmitting the cluster disruptive influenced from water-molecules lying outside the cluster region through cooperative H-bonding⁶. Both these factors lead to a lowering of 'entropy loss' of water in aqueous solutions of aromatic compounds in comparison with those of the analogous aliphatic compounds. This is in agreement with the fact⁷ that 'entropy loss' for the transfer of open chain amines and ethers from the gaseous state (at 1 atm pressure) to dilute aqueous solutions is larger than that for the cyclic analogues. There is thus a lowering of 'local viscosity' and B -term value for aromatic compounds.

Attempt has been made to compare B_{expt} value obtained by fitting the experimental data to the Jones-

Dole equation, with B_{theo} value computed by summing up the B -contributions of all the hydrophilic groups (e.g. carboxylate ion, phenolic OH and $^+\text{NH}_3$) adopting the principle of additivity^{8,9} which has been extended as⁶, $B_{\text{theo}} C = \sum B_i C_i$, where i represents the hydrophilic groups⁶. The lack of concordance between B_{expt} and B_{theo} was explained⁶ considering that the polymer chain was coiled and not unfolded under the experimental conditions so that the whole of the surface area was not exposed to water to affect its local structure through the interactions of the polar head groups of the polymer, and thereby contribute to B_{expt} . It is also reported that $B_{\text{expt}}/B_{\text{theo}}$ ratio should be in the range of exposed surface area of the coiled system to that of the linear chain which was shown, based on certain approximations, to be in the range of $1/\pi$ (Ref. 6). The deviation of the ratio of these B -terms from the 'ideal value' is accounted for by the neglect of the hydrophobic hydration term while computing B_{theo} .

In the present study, two types of humic acids, namely, N-containing and N-free were synthesised by the alkaline oxidative condensation of vanillic acid with an amino acid, and alkaline self-condensation of vanillic acid itself (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Starting materials	Products	Refluxing time (h)
Vanillic acid with L(-)-aspartic acid	HA ₁	1, 2, 5
Vanillic acid with glycine	HA ₂	1, 2, 5
Vanillic acid with L(+)-lysine	HA ₃	1, 2, 5
Vanillic acid (Self condensation)	HA ₄	-, -, 5

Results and Discussion

It is observed for 2 h condensation products (having the lowest E_4/E_6 ratio and hence the highest degree of condensation) that the molar carboxyl acidity is in the order, $\text{HA}_4 \leq \text{HA}_3 < \text{HA}_1 < \text{HA}_2$, whereas the B -term unit is in the order, $\text{HA}_1 < \text{HA}_3 \leq \text{HA}_2 < \text{HA}_4$

The anomaly in the order of B_{expt} and molar acidity is not in agreement with the principle of additivity on the basis of the theoretical view that the individual B -terms of all the hydrophilic groups in the completely unfolded molecular chain only contribute to B -term (theoretical) and hence the magnitude of B -term is dependent on the content of hydrophilic groups as

$$B_{\text{theo}} C = \sum B_i C_i = \sum B_i Y_i MC \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\text{Hence, } B_{\text{theo}} = \sum B_i Y_i M \times 10^{-3}$$

where for any arbitrary concentration of C (g dl^{-1}) of humic acid, if Y_i is the hydrophilic group content (meq g^{-1}), C_i is equal to $Y_i \times 10^{-3} \times MC$ (g dl^{-1}), where M stands for the molecular weight of monovalent hydrophilic group. However, due to such anomaly in the order, it is supposed that another factor is present in B_{expt} term which was not included earlier in the computation of B_{theo} term, and this factor is related to the hydrophobic hydration effect. Indeed, the earlier studies⁶ pointed out this approximation and discussed the need to include this term in order to improve the proposed model⁶.

It has been stated earlier that $[\eta]$, the term obtained from Fuoss-Strauss equation, can be approximated to B -term in the Jones-Dole equation, and it varies with pH^2 . The pH -dependence can be best ascribed to the folding-unfolding phenomenon. For humic acids, folding-unfolding behaviour has been also reported⁶. At any particular pH , where molecular chain is fully coiled, the $B_{\text{expt}}/B_{\text{theo}}$ ratio would be in the range of $1/\pi$ ⁶, where contribution of hydrophobic surface, in terms of its hydration effect, of linear chain towards B_{theo} term in the denominator of the ratio is supposed to be automatically included. Similarly, it can be expected that at any optimum pH where molecular chain is fully exposed, i.e. unfolded as linear chain form, this ratio should be equal to unity due to the fact that all the hydrophobic groups are exposed to water due to unfolding and the hydrophobic hydration effect is also included in B_{expt} term due to unfolding.

Therefore, $1 \geq B_{\text{expt}}/B_{\text{theo}} \geq 1/\pi$, i.e. the ratio varies within two extreme limits depending on the degree of coiling when hydrophobic hydration effect in

B_{expt} and B_{theo} is of similar nature in its contribution towards structure-making effect. But if both the B -terms are different in nature, namely, computation of B_{theo} is under structure-making effect as being directly proportional to hydrophobic surface area, and determination of B_{expt} is under partial loss of structure-making effect due to aromaticity of the polymer chain, then another extreme possibility may arise, namely, $B_{\text{expt}} / B_{\text{theo}} < 1/\pi$. The decrease in B -term ratio from ideal value is due to decrease in B_{expt} value resulting from partial loss of structure-making effect due to aromaticity. So, the B -terms ratio varies under the influence of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic hydration. Moreover, the structure-making effect leads to increase in this ratio whereas loss of this structure-making effect results in a decrease. In the present study, it is observed that for all the synthetic products, this ratio is greater than unity and it is due to the fact that the effect of hydrophobic surface is excluded in the computation of B_{theo} term. The much higher value of B -term ratio than unity indicates the predominating role of hydrophobic surface, comparative study of which is done in terms of structure-making/-breaking phenomenon in what follows.

The surface property study reveals that the higher value of $(-\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$ is the indication of longer un-

folded molecular chain¹⁰ and it should contribute positively to hydrophobic hydration through its structure-making effect resulting in higher B -terms ratio. Again a greater degree of condensation, i.e. more aromatisation, as judged by lower (E_4/E_6) ratio, indicates negative contribution towards hydrophobic hydration through its less structure-making (i.e. more structure-breaking) effect leading to decrease in the B -terms ratio. Therefore, positive $\Delta(\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$ value indicates increase in structure-making effect and negative $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ value indicates increase in structure-breaking (or less structure-making) effect during progress of condensation.

During 1 to 2 h condensation, large decrease in B -term ratio is observed for HA₁ and HA₂. Here the effect of structure-breaking influence of molecular chain predominated over the structure-making effect in hydrophobic hydration as is evident from slight positive change in $(\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$ and greater negative change in E_4/E_6 value, i.e. smaller $\Delta(-\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$ and greater $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ values (in magnitude only). In case of HA₃, increase in B -terms ratio is noticed during 1 to 2 h condensation. Similar comparison among $\Delta(-\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$ and $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ values reveal that structure-making effect of hydrophobic chain is more prominent than structure-breaking effect of aromatic core resulting in

TABLE 2—DATA FOR COMPARATIVE STUDY OF B -TERMS, SURFACE TENSION, SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND pH-METER TITRATION OF SYNTHETIC HUMIC ACIDS

Materials	Period of condensation h	Molar acidity carboxyl $\times 10^{-4}$	B_{expt}		B_{theo}	$B_{\text{expt}}/B_{\text{theo}}$	E_u/E_6	$\Delta(E_4/E_6)$	$\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial \ln C}$	$\Delta\left(-\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial \ln C}\right)$
			Per-cent ⁻¹	dm ³ mol ⁻¹						
HA ₁	1	11.54	0.340	0.089 7	0.003 6	94.4	7.14	-	4.21	-
	2	8.49	0.017	0.009 8	0.001 5	11.3	2.10	-5.04	5.53	+1.32
	5	10.93	0.188	0.087 1	0.002 0	94.0	2.39	+0.29	6.18	+0.65
HA ₂	1	2.79	0.059	0.005 9	0.002 1	28.1	5.81	-	2.06	-
	2	9.57	0.030	0.011 9	0.001 9	15.8	3.20	-2.61	3.37	+1.31
	5	6.87	0.031	0.009 1	0.002 0	15.5	3.65	+0.45	1.22	-2.15
HA ₃	1	3.01	0.111	0.005 5	0.005 5	20.2	4.67	-	1.00	-
	2	3.90	0.036	0.011 7	0.001 5	24.0	4.00	-0.67	5.36	+4.36
	3	3.10	0.026	0.005 6	0.001 6	16.25	4.24	+0.24	5.20	+0.16
HA ₄	5	3.83	0.060	0.043 2	0.004 7	12.8	6.45	-	1.25	-

increase in B -terms ratio. On prolonged condensation from 2 to 5 h, it is observed that there is large increase in B -terms ratio for HA_1 whereas decrease in this ratio is observed for HA_2 and HA_3 . In case of HA_1 , structure-making effect is more prominent due to both increase in hydrophobic chain, i.e. $\Delta(-\delta\gamma\delta \ln C)$ is positive, and decrease in aromatisation, i.e. $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ is also positive. For HA_2 and HA_3 , $\Delta(-\delta\gamma\delta \ln C)$ is sufficiently negative so that there is greater loss in structure-making effect, while there is also slight loss in structure-breaking effect (i.e. slight gain in structure-making effect) as $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ is slightly positive and the large loss in structure-making effect predominates over slight gain in structure-making effect causing a decrease in B -terms ratio.

The B -terms ratio of 2 h synthetic products (having the lowest E_4/E_6 ratio) follows the order, $HA_1 < HA_2 < HA_3$, indicating the order of hydration and it is reverse of the order of aromatisation, i.e. $HA_1 > HA_2 > HA_3$, as is evident from E_4/E_6 ratio. This indicates that structure-breaking effect, induced by aromaticity, mainly governs the order of hydrophobic hydration, so that the respective (E_4/E_6) ratio makes the difference of the B -terms ratios of the humic products. The B -terms ratio is moderate for HA_4 as it is less condensed.

Experimental

Synthesis : Each alkaline condensation material, as stated earlier, was filtered and the filtrate was centrifuged at pH 8.0. The resultant filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl to pH 3.0. The precipitate was centrifuged and purified by repeated extraction and treatment with ion exchange resin¹¹. The resulting suspension was then dialysed with distilled water until no trace of Cl^- ion was left. The products as withdrawn from refluxing bath after each hour interval were analysed through spectrophotometric measurements¹² (i.e. the ratio of optical density at 465 nm to that of 665 nm), and only those products which showed marked change in the optical density ratio from the previous hour products were kept for investigation.

B -term evaluation : The B_{expt} term was determined from viscosity measurement at 30° with an Ostwald

type of viscometer having flow-time of water 150 s for 5 ml. The pH of the humic acid solution was maintained at the pH corresponding to first inflexion point of the respective pH-metric titration curves. The least-squares fitting of the experimental data to the Jones-Dole equation was used for B_{expt} determination. From the B_{expt} value of Na-humate, Na^+ ion contribution ($B_{Na^+} = 0.037$ per cent⁻¹)^{6,8} was subtracted to obtain B -value for humate anion only. The B_{theo} computation was done in a manner as stated earlier. Thus,

$$C = 1 \text{ g dl}^{-1}$$

$$C_{\text{COO}^-} = 2.4 \text{ meq g}^{-1} \text{ (synthetic HA)}$$

$$= 2.4 \times 44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g dl}^{-1}$$

$$C_{\text{phenolic-OH}} = 1.45 \times 17 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g dl}^{-1}$$

and

$$C_{+\text{NH}_3} = 2.55 \times 10^{-2} \times \frac{17}{14} \text{ g dl}^{-1},$$

where 2.55 is the N% in the synthetic product. The values for different hydrophilic groups were taken⁶ as $-B_{\text{COO}^-} = 0.020$, $B_{\text{phenolic-OH}} = -0.024$, $B_{\text{N}+\text{H}_3} = 0.013$ in per cent⁻¹ unit. The resulting B_{theo} turned out to be 0.0018 per cent⁻¹. The unit of B -terms was converted by using the relation⁶,

$$\frac{B \text{ (percent}^{-1}\text{)}}{B \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}} = \frac{1}{0.1 M}$$

where M stands for molecular weight.

Surface tension measurement : It was measured for the synthetic products at 30° by employing a du Nöuy's direct-reading Tensiometer (model 70535). Similar to viscosity study, solutions were prepared at the pH corresponding to the first inflexion point of pH-metric titration curve ($-\delta\gamma\delta \ln C$) was evaluated by least-squares fitting of the surface tension data to the plot γ vs $\ln C$.

Spectrophotometric measurement : The (E_4/E_6) ratio was calculated from the optical density measurement at 465 and 665 nm¹² using a Systronics 106

spectrophotometer. The change in the values of $(-\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$, i.e. $\Delta(-\delta\gamma/\delta \ln C)$, and (E_4/E_6) ratio, i.e. $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$, during progress of condensation were calculated which are tabulated for comparative study in Table 1 along with other parameters.

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